

Anthelmintic Activity of Essential Oils from *Boswellia dalzielii* against *Haemonchus contortus* isolated from Sheep Sold in Gusau Market, Zamfara State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explores the anthelmintic potentials of *Boswellia dalzielii* essential oils (BDOs), specifically targeting *Haemonchus contortus* isolated from sheep sold in Gusau Market Zamfara State, Nigeria. In vitro, anthelmintic activities (egg hatch test – EHT; larval development test – LDT) of *Boswellia dalzielii* essential oils, were conducted. Eggs and larvae of *H. contortus* were exposed to *B. dalzielii* oil at doses of 25 mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, and 100mg/ml for 24hours. The reference drug used for both EHT and LDT was ivermectin (100 mg/ml). In EHT, 100% mortality of *H. contortus* (eggs) were observed after 4hours of treatment with BDOs (50 mg/ml) at LC₅₀ (25mg/ml). While in LDT, 100% mortality of *H. contortus* (larvae) was observed after 24hours of treatment with BDOs (100 mg ml/l) at LC₅₀ (21mg/ml). The results indicate significant differences in EDT and LDT of BDOs on *Haemonchus contortus* eggs and larvae (P ≤0.05). The findings of this work indicate that BDOs have anthelmintic potency on *Haemonchus contortus* eggs and larvae in sheep sold in Gusau, and it could contribute valuable insights into developing sustainable and natural methods for controlling parasitic infections in livestock, offering potential benefits for both animal health and the agricultural community particularly in Zamfara State.

Keywords: Anthelmintic activity, *Boswellia dalzielii*, Essential oils, Gusau, *Haemonchus contortus*, Zamfara state.

1.0Introduction

Haemonchus contortus is the most commercially significant and pathogenic gastrointestinal nematode parasite in small ruminants globally [1]. For livestock producers, the major economic loss in productivity and revenue is caused by a spike in resistance to commercial anthelmintic drugs [2] hence, the urgent need for new plant-derived compounds based on reliable *in vivo* and *in vitro* screening tests capable of detecting potentially active products [3]. The excessive use of synthetic anthelmintic drugs for treating diseases and infections has led to widespread resistance in nematodes [4]. This situation underscores the need for the creation of innovative anthelmintics with distinct mechanisms of action [5]. Barbervax® (Bvax) is the first commercially available vaccine for the control of *Haemonchus contortus* infection in sheep and was registered for use in Australia in 2014 [6], but vaccines against helminths have yet to achieve a prominent role in worm control [7]. Since *Haemonchus contortus*

has developed a resistance to the majority of anthelmintic classes, there has been a significant demand for new compounds against this parasite and related nematodes [8], as well as the need to create alternative ethnoveterinary therapies for the treatment and management of haemonchosis [9]. Plant-derived anthelmintics are a promising alternative to synthetic deworming drugs because, until the mid-20th century, livestock producers in rural communities relied on plant-based methods of grazing herbal leys, specific medicinal tree leaves, and rotational grazing to minimize parasite burdens [10]. Miró et al. [11] reported that the anthelmintic effects of plant-derived bioactive phytochemical compounds either alone or in combination with synthetic drugs as pharmacological tools for improving nematode control in livestock have only been scantily explored *in vivo*. The Burseraceae plays a crucial role as a family of trees and shrubs that produce resin, resulting in essential oils with biological activity. Within this family, *Boswellia dalzielii* and *Canarium schweinfurthii* are utilized in West

African traditional medicine to address various health conditions [12].

The Burseraceae family comprises 18 genera and approximately 640 species, primarily consisting of tropical trees and shrubs. Notable members with historical and commercial significance include frankincense (*Boswellia spp.*) and myrrh (*Commiphora myrrha*). Among these genera, such as *Boswellia*, *Bursera*, *Canarium*, *Commiphora*, *Dacryodes*, and *Protium*, various biologically active essential oils have been extracted. The genus *Boswellia*, found in Africa, the Arabian Peninsula, and India, is particularly known for producing the aromatic oleogum resin frankincense. *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch, a species native to West Africa, extends from western Chad through Nigeria and Burkina Faso to Mali. Traditional medicine has employed bark decoctions of *B. dalzielii* for treating diverse ailments, including malaria, toothaches, sores, abscesses, mental disorders, yellow fever, asthma, wounds, and dysentery. Additionally, the leaves of *B. dalzielii* have been utilized to safeguard stored food from insect pests [13]. There is potential for the treatment of infections caused by gastrointestinal nematodes through the use of essential oils and other herbal medicines [14].

A lot of research has been done on the *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* studies of the anthelmintic properties of plant-derived extracts; however, there is a dearth of documented studies on the *in vitro* antihelminthic properties of essential oils from *Boswellia dalzielii* against *Haemonchus contortus* in sheep, particularly in Gusau Local government area of Zamfara State.

2.0 Materials and Methods

A preliminary investigation was conducted to elicit information on the use of ethno-veterinary plant essential oils and extracts used as an alternative herb, method of preparation, and extraction for the treatment of helminthiasis in sheep.

2.1. Plant collection and identification

Fresh leaves of *Boswellia dalzielii* were collected and transferred to the Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara state Nigeria. Identification was done by botanists and plant taxonomists in the herbarium section of the department.

2.2. Sources of Animals and Management

The study population comprised twenty (25) sheep showing clinical signs (weight loss, anemia, and weakness) between the ages of 8-24 months as described in the procedures of Ademola et al. [15]

2.3 Plant preparation and Extraction of essential oils

The fresh leaves of *Boswellia dalzielii* were gently rinsed under running water to remove any impurities and spread in a single layer in a well-ventilated area away from direct sunlight. The leaves were allowed to wilt or partially dry for a few hours. Before extraction, the leaves were chopped to enhance oil release. Essential oils were then extracted from the fresh leaves using the Soxhlet extraction method with n-hexane at the Department of Chemistry, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State.

2.4. *In vitro* anthelmintic Test

Methods described by Štrbac et al. [14] were adopted for evaluation of *in vitro* anthelmintic activity and all the experiments were performed in triplicate. The brief descriptions along with minor modifications are as follows.

2.4.1. *In vitro* egg hatch test (EHT):

The *in vitro* egg hatch test involved the recovery of eggs from fecal samples collected from the rectal ampulla of sheep with a natural-mixed infection. The samples were processed within 2 hours of collection using the recovery technique described by Štrbac et al. [14]. Fecal samples were homogenized and filtered under running water through meshes of different mesh sizes (1 mm, 250, 212, and 38 μ m) to separate the nematode eggs from the feces. Eggs retained on the last sieve were washed and centrifuged for 3 min at 1500 rpm with distilled water, after which the supernatant was discarded. Centrifugation was performed using a 40% sugar solution to float the eggs, which was then isolated into new tubes and mixed with distilled water. Centrifugation of the solution twice was done to remove pellets and obtain an aqueous solution with the *Haemonchus contortus* eggs. Twenty-four wells, plates containing aqueous solutions of approximately 50 eggs/well. Three concentrations of each tested essential oil sample (100, 50, and 25 mg/ml) were emulsified and completed with distilled water in a final volume of 0.5 ml/well. The preparations were incubated for 48 h at 27 °C, after which the

number of eggs and first-stage larvae (L1) was counted under an inverted microscope. The obtained values were expressed as the mean percentage of the egg-hatching inhibition. A positive control drug of ivermectin (100 mg/ml) was used. The experiment was replicated and the mean values were taken.

2.4.2. *In vitro* larval development test (LDT):

The infective larvae were obtained by stool culture from the feces of Sheep donors previously infested by *H. contortus* larvae. The feces were collected directly from the sheep's rectum. The eggs contained in the fecal matter were subsequently placed in stool culture at room temperature for 7 days. At the end of this culture time, the larvae were extracted from the fecal mass.

2.4.2.1 Evaluation of larvicidal activity of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils

Twenty-six, thirty, and twenty-nine larvae (L3) were counted and an average was calculated to give twenty-eight (28) (L3) larvae which were distributed into each well of a 24-flatbottomed microtitre plate at different concentrations (25, 50 and 100 mg/ml). *Boswellia dalzielii* oils and positive control of albendazole were dissolved in Phosphate buffer saline (PBS). PBS was used as a negative control. The plates were incubated for 24 and 48 hours at 27°C. The experiment was replicated three times for each extract on the same plate. After the incubation period, the number of dead larvae was counted under the microscope.

The percentage of mortality (Mt%) was determined using the following formula: $Mt\% = \left(\frac{\text{Number of dead larvae}}{\text{Number of larvae in culture}} \right) \times 100$

2.4.2.2. Data analysis

The percentage mortality calculated was analyzed by ANOVA to check the differences among treatment groups. Data Obtained from EHT and LDT were subjected to probit analysis for estimation of lethal concentration (LC).

3.0 Results

3.1 *In vitro* Egg Hatch Test (EHT) of *Boswellia dalzielii* oil (BDO)

The results show an increase in concentrations of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils increased mortality rates of *H. contortus* eggs. Table 3.1 shows the ovicidal activities of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils on *H. contortus* after 4 hours. At 25mg/ml of BDO treatment, the mean ovicidal activity was 90%. While at 50 and 100 mg/ml of oil treatments, the mean ovicidal activity was 100%.

Table 3.2 presents the results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the ovicidal activities of different *Boswellia dalzielii* oil treatments on *Haemonchus contortus*. The results indicate that there are significant differences in the ovicidal activities of *Boswellia dalzielii* oil treatment on *Haemonchus contortus* eggs ($P \leq 0.05$) at LC_{50} (25mg/ml)

Table 3.1 Ovicidal activity of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils on *H. contortus* eggs after 4hours

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
25 mg/ml	90 ^b	1.00	77.30	103
50 mg/ml	100 ^a	.000	100	100
100 mg/ml	100 ^a	.000	100	100
Total	73	15.80	34.91	110

Figure 3.1. Probit analysis of *B. dalzielii* oil ovicidal activity (EHT) on *H. contortus* eggs at LC_{50} (21mg/ml) after 4 hours

3.2 *In vitro* larval development test (LDT) of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils

Based on the present results, an increase in concentrations of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils increases the mortality rates in *H. contortus* larvae. Table 3.3 presents the results of the larvicidal activities of *B. dalzielii* oil treatments and time intervals on the mortality rate of 28 larvae of *H. contortus* that were exposed to treatment. Mortality rates were

observed after 24 hours. For treatment with 25 mg/ml, the mean larvicidal activity was 2(7%). For treatment with 50 mg/ml, 6 (21%) of the parasite died. At 24 hours, none of the 28 larvae of *H. contortus* exposed for this experiment survived. For treatment with 100 mg/ml, 21 out of 28 larvae (75%) mortality rates were recorded. After 24 hours, all 28 larvae used for the experiment died.

Table 3.2 Larvicidal activity of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils on *H. contortus* larvae after 24hours

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
25 mg/ml	9 .0 ^b	.78	7.68	10.92
50 mg/ml	27.0 ^a	.78	24.98	28.22
100 mg/ml	25.0 ^a	.78	23.78	27.02

Figure 3.2 Probit analysis of *B.dalzielii* oil larvicidal activity (LDT) on *H. contortus* Larvae at LC_{50} (25mg/ml) after 24 hours

4.0 Discussion

In vitro egg hatch test (EHT) of *Boswellia dalzielii* oil (BDO)

Utilizing plant-derived substances like essential oils in anthelmintic treatments offers numerous benefits. Firstly, essential oils (EOs) possess a diverse chemical composition containing various bioactive compounds with significant pharmacological potential [16]. This composition contributes to their potent activity against nematodes, as demonstrated in our *in vitro* study. Additionally, the abundance of compounds in essential oils belonging to different chemical classes may decrease susceptibility to resistance [17,18]. The use of suitable techniques is necessary for evaluating the anthelmintic efficacy of EOs. For this study, the essential oils from *Boswellia dalzielii* tested showed high ovicidal (90%) at a concentration of 25 mg/l after 4 hours. According to recommendations by the World Association (WAAVP, 2022 and 2023), potential anthelmintics are considered highly effective when their efficacy exceeds 98%, effective when they average in the range 90–98%, moderately effective in the range 80–89% and ineffective when efficacy is less than 80%. These findings were similar to studies on *Eucalyptus staigeriana* EO, which inhibited 99.27% of *H. contortus* egg hatching at 1.35 mg mL⁻¹ and 99.20% larval development at 5.4 mg mL⁻¹ [19]. The maximum inhibition effectiveness rates of *Eucalyptus globulus* EO on egg hatching and larval development were 99.3% at 21.75 and 98.7% at 43.5 mg mL⁻¹, respectively [19].

Zhu et al [20], performed an experiment similar to this study, using the *Artemisia lancea* EOs and its major constituents, 1,8-cineol, and camphor. The oil of *A. lancea* and 1,8-cineol at a dose of 10 mg/ml had an ovicidal activity of 99.4% and 74.8% and LC_{50} of 1.82 and 4.64 mg/ml, respectively. When comparing the results obtained in this study, it can be said that the solutions tested here had more action, since the inhibition of hatching was 100% at LC_{50} (21mg/l). Therefore, *Boswellia dalzielii* oils were highly effective against *H. contortus* eggs

Larvicidal activities of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils

This study furthered the investigation of the larvicidal activities of *B. dalzielii* oil according to time intervals on the mortality and survival rates of *H. contortus*. The treatments involving different oil doses of 25 mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, and 100 mg/ml were administered. At 24 hours, the larvicidal potentials were attained (100%), while the least concentration of *B. dalzielii* oils at LC_{50} (21mg/ml) was observed. Similar studies were observed in *Eucalyptus globulus* essential oil with 98.7% larval development at concentrations of 21.75 and 43.5 mg/ml [19]. *Croton zehntneri* and *Lippia sidoides* essential oils inhibited 99.2 and 94.5% larval development of *H. contortus* at concentrations of 10 and 20 mg/ml [21]. Some plant essential oils are effective in killing both the larvae and adults of *Haemonchus contortus* within 24 hours due to their anthelmintic activity. These oils contain biologically active compounds that are effective against the parasite. Some botanical families, such as Zingiberaceae, Verbenaceae,

Laminaceae, and Euphorbiaceae, are known to exhibit biological activity against *H. contortus*. Essential oils extracted from both native Amazonian and exotic species have been screened in vitro for anthelmintic activity against *H. contortus* eggs and larvae. According to Magaji and Yaro (2006) and Yongwa et al. [22, 23], the anthelmintic activity of plants is attributed to the secondary metabolites present in plants respectively polyphenols; flavonoids, and tannins. To this end, these plant metabolites may have worked in combination or singly to cause inhibition of egg hatch and larval mortality that were observed in this work. According to Štrbac et al. [14] the essential oil of the peppermint showed higher activity of EOs against *H. contortus* in comparison with *Trichostrongylus spp.* after per-oral administration of the formulations, suggesting that there may be differences in sensitivity on EOs within the GIN genera (e.g., due to their position in the gastrointestinal tract).

5.0 Conclusion

The results obtained shows the ovicidal (90%) and larvicidal (100%) activities of *Boswellia dalzielii* oil on *H. contortus* after 4 hours and 24hours at LC₅₀ (25 mg/ml and 21 mg/ml) respectively. Also, an increase in concentrations of *Boswellia dalzielii* oils increased the mortality rates of *H. contortus* eggs and larvae. The results indicates that there are significant differences in *Boswellia dalzielii* oil treatment on *Haemonchus contortus* eggs and larvae ($P \leq 0.05$). The information from this study contributes to the broader understanding of *B. dalzielii* oil as a potential eco-friendly solution for controlling target eggs, larvae, and adult populations of parasites.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that herders in Gusau, Zamfara state should be informed about the medicinal significance of *Boswellia dalzielli* oil and its phytochemical constituents. They should also be encouraged to administer this essential oil to sheep, goats, and other livestock against gastrointestinal helminthes. Future studies should focus on the structural profiling and characterization of the bioactive components with anthelmintic properties. Additionally, *in vivo* studies are recommended to validate the anthelmintic activity of *Boswellia dalzielli* essential oil.

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest.

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